

Developing of a Performance Comparison Index for Image Super-Resolution Models

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ABSTRACT

Super-resolution techniques refer to the field that deals with enhancing the quality of low-resolution images. The greatest challenge in developing super-resolution models is the measurement of the resolution. The study area of image quality enhancements provides many indexes and metrics to evaluate an image's quality. However, most of the state-of-the-art solutions are heavily dependent on the spatial features of images and overlook the patterns inside the image.

In our research, we propose a new comparison index which measures the quality of images by their harmonic structures. We carry the basis of the problem to frequency analysis and deliver the solution iteratively with structural similarity. Thus, with the solution we have created, we hope to contribute to the field of super-resolution research and eliminate the disadvantages of current methods.

We share the implementation of the comparison index we have proposed in an open-source manner and provide significant improvements over traditional methods such as SSIM and PSNR by performing experimentations using the implementation.

Keywords: Fourier magnitudes, harmonics analysis, super-resolution, image quality assessment

ABBREVIATIONS

BMP	Bitmap
CVPR	Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition
DC	Direct Current
DFT	Discrete Fourier Transform
DSSIM	Difference Structural Similarity Index
ESRGAN	Enhanced Super-Resolution Generative Adversarial Networks
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FSIM	Feature Similarity Index
GAN	Generative Adversarial Networks
HAT	Hybrid Attention Transformer
HRI	Harmonics Radius Index
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
JPEG	Joint Photographic Experts Group
MSE	Mean Squared Error
NTIRE	New Trends in Image Restoration and Enhancement
PEP	Python Enhancement Proposals
PIRM	Perceptual Image Super-Resolution
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
PSNR	Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio
SAFe	Scaled Agile Framework
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Assignable, Realistic, Time-Related
SSIM	Structural Similarity Index
TIFF	Tagged Image File Format
VIF	Visual Information Fidelity

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Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

The field of improving the quality of a low-resolution image is called super-resolution techniques. Many academics have researched this study area since the beginning of the 80s, and it became increasingly popular after the rise of artificial intelligence [4].

The research of image quality enhancement methods introduces two main questions: *the limits of improving image quality* and *the representation of the quality of any image*. In this thesis, we address the second inquiry and propose a methodology for numerically expressing the resolution of an image in terms of its perceptual attributes.

1.1 Thesis Background

There needs to be more clarity in people's minds when discussing the resolution term. Most people mainly focus on pixel sizes whenever there is a need to compare different images or videos. However, within the following Figure 1.1, we can easily disprove the common sense of quality.

1.1.1 Image Quality and its Resolution

The images in Figure 1.1 are one of the very famous test images in the field of image processing, called Lenna. The one on the left is the original one with the dimensions 512×512 and 521 KB in file size using PNG 8-bit color depth. Conversely, it is a reconstructed version using a linear interpolation technique to increase the resolution from 128×128 to 512×512. Its file size is 359 KB and uses PNG 8-bit colour depth. Despite the file sizes, there is no exact difference in quality between the images for a computer. However, the human eyes can quickly identify the difference and may call the right one “blurry”.

Figure 1.1: Reference image 'Lenna' that is 512x512 in size on the left, and its reconstructed version from 128x128 to 512x512 by using linear interpolation on the right.

The need for a numerical comparison method for an image's qualities has become more critical with developments in artificial intelligence. Since the training phase of developing an AI model is dependent on the choice of cost function, one of the leading research concerns is finding the best cost function to be used in super-resolution comparison.

1.1.2 Image Quality Indexes and Metrics

Many indexes or metrics are developed to assess a number for comparing the images. Today, the widely used ones in the field of study are the Structural Similarity (SSIM) Index, the Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), the Mean Squared Error (MSE), and the Visual Information Fidelity (VIF). These metrics and indexes can be categorized as full-reference, reduce-reference, and no-reference methods.

The full-reference methods use techniques to compare the constructed images with their true (reference) images. Because the no-reference methods do not require a reference image, they are generally more complex than the full-reference methods. As a middle point from the two sides, reduce-reference methods use segmentation and feature extraction to provide a numerical value for quality assessment.

Mean Squared Error (MSE) is a basic metric that is used in wide-spread areas in signal processing. It uses the average squared difference between each sample of the signal. The pixels of the reference and reconstructed images are what these samples are for image processing. Lower MSE values indicate better quality.

The Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) measures the maximum power of a signal regarding the power of the noise that corrupts the accuracy of the true signal. It provides a better scale due to its logarithmic function but is widely criticized for not aligning with human visual perception. Higher PSNR values are associated with higher quality.

The Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) is one of the most used metrics, which produces results between -1 and 1, where the perfect similarity is the highest. It is designed to consider human visual system features, such as brightness, contrast, and structure, strong enough to handle noise and compression artefacts. The feature similarity index (FSIM) is one of the modifications to the SSIM that considers the local phase information to detect distortions at the structural level. Unlike SSIM, the Difference Structural Similarity Index (DSSIM) demonstrates differences instead of similarities between images.

Visual Information Fidelity (VIF) takes a more general approach by considering structural similarities and statistical features simultaneously. This method is a step up from the SSIM method.

The difficulty of conventionally used methods is their dependence on spatial features. It results in a significant drawback of classifying a reconstructed image's quality score as low whenever pixel shifts or rotations are compared to the reference image. Hence, developing novel algorithms or artificial intelligence models for super-resolution research necessitates the development of an index or metric unaffected by structural differences and can accurately convey the quality of a comprehensive picture.

1.1.3 Frequency Domain Representation

Using the frequency domain in signal analysis is common practice to eliminate spatial features such as structural shifts, visual distortion, and rotation-based changes. A signal can be represented as a sum of sinusoidal components with various amplitudes, frequencies, and phases. Each sinusoidal element is described as *harmonics*.

The Fourier Transform is a mathematical technique that converts the spatial domain into the frequency domain in continuous time signals. It is a reversible method that allows scientists to experiment in the frequency domain and see the changes in the spatial domain. The discrete Fourier Transform alters the domains in digital signals, acting as a slight tweak to the original Fourier Transform. Computer hardware advancements allow us to perform these transitions in real time.

Using Equation 1.1, we calculate all the harmonics of an image with $M \times N$ dimensions.

$$F(u, v) = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} f(m, n) \cdot e^{-j2\pi(\frac{um}{M} + \frac{vn}{N})} \quad (1.1)$$

In Equation 1.1, $F(u, v)$ is the image represented in the frequency domain, $f(u, v)$ is the image represented in the spatial domain, M is the number of pixels in one dimension, and N is the number of pixels in the other dimension.

To return from the frequency domain, one can use Equation 1.2 and calculate the pixel values. The same abbreviations are used in the equation as the previous DFT equation.

$$f(m, n) = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_{u=0}^{M-1} \sum_{v=0}^{N-1} F(u, v) \cdot e^{j2\pi(\frac{um}{M} + \frac{vn}{N})} \quad (1.2)$$

In Figure 1.2, the image of Lenna is inputted into Equation 1.1, and the resulting complex harmonics values' magnitudes and phases are shown. The brightest points in the middle of the magnitudes represent the frequencies with the most-valued amplitudes, and the brightest point in the centre of the image is called the DC component, which is harmonic with no frequency.

Figure 1.2: The original image of Lenna on the left. The magnitude of the harmonics in logarithmic scale shown in the middle. The right part is the phases of the harmonics.

Figure 1.3 and Figure 1.4 is designed to show the difference between the magnitudes and the phases of harmonics. A magnitude is a strength of frequency that stores information about the existence of patterns and helps us to characterize the texture content. On the other hand, a phase stores the spatial arrangement of patterns. In consideration of the patterns as information, one can see that the filtering operation on magnitudes removes some of the patterns, hence the details of the image. However, the removal operation on the phases does not remove the patterns since the small textures that can be seen on high-resolution images

still exist. Filtering processes made on the phase side only changed the colour perspective for the human perception.

Figure 1.3: The change in the spatial domain after applying a 1-dimensional Hamming filter in the harmonics' magnitudes.

1.1.4 Proposed Solution to the Drawbacks of Common Quality Indexes

As discussed earlier in subsection 1.1.2, the conventional methods of image quality assessments are based on structural analysis. It is a significant drawback when the image has been shifted or rotated due to the low scoring on these indexes. In this thesis, we propose a new method to evaluate the quality of an image by the number of harmonics with a high influence on the image. This technique is a full-reference method, where it can be extended to no-reference methodology in future work.

Within this new index, we want to solve the problems of assessment of quality without considering the features dependent on the pixel's location, but instead the patterns in the image. This new quality comparison technique will considerably affect the training of

Figure 1.4: The change in the spatial domain after applying a 1-dimensional Hamming filter in the harmonics' phases.

super-resolution models and continuing image enhancement research.

1.2 Project Definition

This section describes the problem and defines the completion criteria. Additionally, we discuss the scope of the project and what needs to be covered.

1.2.1 Problem Statement

The problem we aim to solve is to create a numerical index that can compare two or more super-resolution methods and provide help on cost function design for deep learning models. The numerical index must provide information regarding the image's quality and the spatial features should be ignored as much as possible.

1.2.2 Context and Scope

Super-resolution is the family of methods for enhancing the quality of low-resolution images. It has been researched for over 30 years and is gaining momentum after the advances in the area of artificial intelligence study. While the state-of-art has already been searching for the best method to increase quality, there still needs to be a question of the representation of the quality itself. This thesis undertakes the challenge of the question and suggests a methodology for expressing resolution in terms of its perceptual features.

The modern super-resolution articles primarily focus on widely accepted indexes such as Structural Similarity (SSIM) Index, Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), Mean Squared Error (MSE), and Visual Information Fidelity (VIF). While these metrics are valuable in numerous aspects, regularly, they rely heavily on spatial features. Dependence on spatial-domain metrics leads to challenges in accurately judging image quality, especially image resolution, in the discourse of super-resolution.

Table 1.1: Comparison of Image Quality Indexes

Index	Components	Sensitivity	Use Cases
MSE	Pixel-wise differences	Sensitive to large errors, not aligned with human perception	Widely used for simplicity
PSNR	Global pixel-wise differences	Sensitive to large errors, somehow aligns with human perception	Image and video compression algorithms
SSIM	Luminance, contrast, structure similarity	Robust to common distortions, aligns with human perception	Image compression, reconstruction, and enhancement
FSIM	Local phase information	More sensitive to distortions compared to SSIM	Image quality assessment on specific features or characteristics
DSSIM	Opposite of SSIM	Emphasizes differences; highlights variations	Image difference detection, segmentation
VIF	Structural and statistical information	Comprehensive analysis, aligns more with human perception	Image restoration, compression, enhancement
Proposed	Patterns on the image	Less sensitive to structural changes, emphasizes whole image	Image super-resolution comparison

Table 1.1 summarizes the differences between the current evaluation methods and the perspective of the need to create a new index.

The index can be classified as done if the requirements below are fulfilled.

- The index must evaluate the image quality of a reconstructed image based on the harmonics difference within a reference image.
- The index must be a full-reference image quality method.
- The index must provide a number that is meaningful for computer algorithms.
- The index must be consistent with its previous scores on the same image.
- The index must identify a structurally differentiated image as nearly the same as the non-differentiated one.

1.2.3 Significance and Implications

There are numerous drawbacks to the current image quality metrics and indexes due to the nature of their spatial features. We've experimented on an image to see the drawback of the Structural Similarity Index, one of the most used indexes in the image enhancement area of research. Figure 1.5 shows the same picture of Lenna, but one with its mirrored version on both the x- and y-axis.

Figure 1.5: Experimenting on SSIM's Drawbacks.

The SSIM score is calculated from the image's parameters, such as luminance, contrast, pixel variance. Within the experiment on Figure 1.5, we found that the SSIM score for the

image on the left is 0.8046, which is comparably high and can be considered as a good quality. However, the same image's mirrored version without any additional modification resulted in 0.3200 on the SSIM scale. It proves that the SSIM scoring system does not consider human perception. The same image but from different angles of view presents drastic changes in scale.

A new index for the image quality comparison problem needs to solve this issue on SSIM and other indexes. These changes in our look to quality terms, from spatial to frequency domain, will help many researchers and provide a realistic scale for their work. Despite the experiment we have conducted with mirror images and their non-practical result, having super-resolution models that predict shifted image results is ignored with current cost functions. This thesis provides a better way to compare image qualities to research super-resolution areas.

This transition to the frequency domain provides a more robust and perceptually meaningful metric for comparing image qualities, especially crucial in the context of training artificial intelligence models for super-resolution. The study's scientific significance lies in its potential to reshape the landscape of image quality assessment, offering a more accurate and reliable index for researchers in the pursuit of advancing super-resolution methods and image enhancement techniques.

The proposed methodology presents a unique approach by measuring image quality based on the number of harmonics with high impact, thus shifting the focus from pixel-dependent features to overall image patterns. This transition to the frequency domain provides a more robust and perceptually meaningful metric for comparing image qualities, especially crucial in training artificial intelligence models for super-resolution. The study's scientific significance lies in its potential to reshape the future of image quality assessment, offering a more accurate and reliable index for researchers in advancing super-resolution methods and image enhancement techniques.

We believe this new index would also impact video super-resolution research by solving the problem of small camera movements on sequent frames.

1.3 Possible Challenges

The definition of done for the scope of this new approach is described in sub-section 1.2.2. The next move must be to indicate the possible challenges we may face while developing this index.

The biggest challenge would be creating an algorithm that measures the harmonics count and provides a reliable numeric result. We could ask ourselves the question of what a "high-impact" harmonic is and what the specification that differentiates it from an unimpactful one is. Therefore, we need to be extra careful on designin our solution.

Another challenge would be making it robust and fast as much as possible. Robustness is a critical must for engineering solutions that many others may use. We would desire fastness for the needs of video super-resolution search. The algorithm needs to be real-time, thus allowing the users the minimum time for training and inferencing and robust to give the same result for each time on the same input.

Challenges are not only limited to the algorithm design part but also to the testing part. We need to create as many tests as possible to ensure the algorithm's robustness and correctness. While most tests require little time, the super-resolution model training will consume many days and costly hardware. We count this problem as the most significant challenge on our way.

Chapter 2

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

The project's objectives are defined in this section to provide a plan that aligns with SAFE and SMART principles. The section on research objectives is a guide for future directions.

- **Objective 1:** Image Transformation to Frequency Domain
 - By the first quarter of the project, we will be able to calculate the transformed model of any image using the Fast Fourier Transform.
 - We plan to use the widely-used Python frameworks to calculate the FFT of an image in the spatial domain.
 - The objective is to create a function block which reads an image in NumPy N-dimensional array format that represents a grayscale image, calculate its frequency representation using the Fast Fourier Transform and return the magnitudes of the resulting complex values in both linear and log-scale.
 - It should be done before the project's first quarter, considerably in the first two weeks.

- **Objective 2:** Deciding on "Meaningful" Harmonics Calculation Algorithm
 - By the first quarter of the project, we will need to decide on the algorithm that calculates the "meaningful" or "high-impact" harmonics.
 - The algorithm can be a full-reference or no-reference method but provide a convenient result on the already-known problems.
 - The objective is to create a pseudo-code algorithm that receives an image's frequency domain magnitudes with/without reference image and provides a numerical result on its harmonics amount. These numerical results must align

with the previous results and rely on scientific background. The main area of focus will be comparison-based calculations such as full-reference image quality indexing methods.

- It should be done in two weeks in the first quarter of the project.
- **Objective 3: Programming the First Demo of the New Index Algorithm**
 - By the end of the first quarter, the pseudo-code and the algorithm already designed must be programmed, and the first results must be investigated.
 - We will achieve this goal using a scripting language, Python, and open-source packages such as NumPy, Matplotlib, and OpenCV. Ultimately, the program would receive an image with/without its reference and write the numerical index value into the standard output.
 - The objective is to have a program to calculate our designed index. This program will be used for the tests to see the initial results of the index. It should provide the same result for the same inputs with a 5% error. The program must accept all types of image formats and image dimensions.
 - It should be done in the last two weeks of the first quarter of the project. Investigating the results and improving the prototype may consume extra time.
- **Objective 4: Providing a Tool for Super Resolution Comparison Indexes**
 - By the first three weeks of the second quarter of the project, we need to have a tool to compare various indexes and metrics.
 - To achieve this goal, we need to create a tool with Python scripting language that accepts an image, calculates its downsampled version and upsamples with different upsamplers, including super-resolution models. As a result, this tool should use SSIM, MSE, PSNR and our proposed solution to find the image quality index.
 - The objective will be done using design patterns such as Facade and Strategy. Each upsampling and downsampling technique will calculate new images within a proxy pattern. Afterwards, the metrics and indexes will be passed into a context manager using a strategy pattern. The context manager will calculate all the indexes and redirect the results into standard output. The tool must be published on GitHub with an open-source license.

- This objective must be done in the first three weeks of the second quarter of the project.
- **Objective 5: Creating Test Images on State-of-Art Super Resolution Models**
 - By the middle of the third quarter, we need two or more super-resolution artificial intelligence models to test our index.
 - To achieve this goal, we must decide on two or more state-of-the-art super-resolution models with a dataset with a wide range of images. The same dataset must be used to train the super-resolution models. Afterwards, these models with nearest neighbour, linear and bicubic interpolation will be used to see the index's results.
 - First, we will decide on two articles in image super-resolution. These articles must be widely known or state-of-art. Afterwards, we need to find a dataset with a variety of images to train these models on the same dataset with the same number of iterations. The training part will be done using expensive hardware and may take time. With the models, we will apply the SSIM, MSE, PSNR and our proposed index to see the performance of each super-resolution technique.
 - Due to the cost of training, we may lose much time by investigating the training process. The objective must be fulfilled before the third quarter's last week of the project.
- **Objective 6: Adjusting the Index Algorithm**
 - By the end of the third quarter, we need to finalize the comparison indexing algorithm details and decide on the interface at the user level.
 - To achieve this goal, we must adjust the parameters used in the tool and the new comparison index's algorithm and align them with our missions. These adjustments may include interface changes on the user level.
 - The objective will be finished when the results seem efficient and reasonable. The advisor and the authors need to decide on the interface details, which will be explained in the thesis.
 - This objective must be finished in a week, and assumably in the last week of the third quarter.
- **Objective 7: Calculating the Proposed Index's Limits**

- By the middle of the last quarter, we need to test the limits of the index, such as frame per second and the maximum and minimum value of the limit.
 - To achieve this goal, we will create a test suite that will run our tool with only our new index calculations on several images, and the average frames per second will be calculated. We expect the tool to run better than the 20FPS rate. As a side objective, the index's maximum and minimum limits will be calculated and checked if they are aligned with the algorithm design.
 - The objective will be finished if the algorithm runs above 20 frames per second and the index limits are aligned with the mathematical background.
 - It is designed to be finished in the first two weeks of the last quarter of the project.
- **Objective 8: Writing the Thesis**
 - By the end of the last quarter, we need to decide on the thesis's read flow and finish its writing.
 - To achieve the goal, we need to create a boilerplate flow for the sections and the subsections with the questions we want to answer inside. Afterwards, we must prepare our working environment for the L^AT_EX-based thesis writing.
 - This objective will be counted as finished whenever the report and the poster are submitted.
 - It is designed to be finished in the last two weeks of the last quarter of the project.

2.1 Project Specifications

This part of the study will present the project's technical requirements in five subfields. The specifications defined in each field can be considered a planning section for the requirements. As a start, we will explain the performance expectations to create an overview of what we want from the project. Then, we will design the technical needs to meet the expectations.

Design elements are the components of the architecture of the project. Each design element provides a functionality that can be worked on its own. The compatibility subsection would describe the need for integration with the community. In this project, security is not a concern and will not be investigated as in others.

Table 2.1: Project Specifications Subfields

Subfield	Description
Performance Expectations	Requirements directly influence the results
Technical Needs	The design choices to meet performance expectations
Design Elements & Functionalities	Splitted components which works by their own
Compatibility	Making the project aligned with the community standards
Security Measures	Consideration of the security leaches and data laws

2.1.1 Performance Expectations

Designing an index needs strict performance requirements. In this subsection, we have listed the minimum requirements that needs to be fit on project development.

- The algorithm shall give the same result on each run with an error rate 5%.
- The algorithm shall work with all types of images and dimensions.
- The algorithm calculations such as Fast Fourier Transform, harmonics count shall be correctly made.
- The algorithm shall run faster or equal than 20 frames per second.
- The algorithm shall align with the other metrics as much as possible.
- The program and algorithm shall be capable of running on each computing platform.

2.1.2 Technical Needs

In order to fulfil the expectations, we need several technical needs. These needs are listed in below.

- The algorithm shall be able to calculate a "meaningful" (or "impactful") harmonics count or provide a similar result where it can interpret the quality.

- The algorithm shall be written in already-proven libraries to overcome engineering problems and to ensure engineering standards.
- The algorithm shall be encapsulated inside an open-source tool to enable the community to use the designed index easily.
- The algorithm shall be tested with different test scenarios.
- The algorithm shall be used to compare two or more super-resolution artificial intelligence model's qualities to provide a use case for the thesis.
- A dataset pair shall be designed to train the super-resolution models with the same data.
- A tool shall generate downscaled (low-resolution) images and upscale them with interpolation methods such as nearest neighbour, linear and bicubic interpolation.

2.1.3 Design Elements & Functionalities

Objectives, needs and expectations can be easily met with the divide-and-conquer method. This method suggests that if a wholesome design can be divided into smaller components, this component development and testing can be quickly done.

- **The Index Algorithm:** The logic behind the index is the main point of the system design. Most of the requirements and needs must be met in this component.
- **A Tool to Test The Algorithm:** This tool will provide a way to test our proposed index and well-known indexes (SSIM, PSNR, MSE). Apart from these calculations, it must provide functionalities to upscale and downscale the given images.
- **Trained Super Resolution Models with The Same Configuration:** To show the first results on the index's usage, we must have two state-of-the-art artificial intelligence models configured with the same number of iterations and trained with the same dataset.
- **Test Cases:** Every system needs unit-, integration- and system-tests. In this component, we must create system tests such as comparing metrics, different upscaling techniques and having the same image with spatial domain-based modifications to test our index.

2.1.4 Compatibility

The proposed solution will create an impact on the super-resolution studies. However, having a considerable impact does not come with significant usage. Mainly, the acceptance of a project heavily depends on alignment with community standards. In this subsection, we have listed the community and engineering standards we will follow.

- The algorithm shall be expressed in pseudo-code format to put more understanding with abstracting the programming language.
- The algorithm and the tool shall be designed and programmed using Python scripting language with following the PEP-8 standards. It will help the community easily integrate the index into their tools.
- The programming style of the tool shall be examined with linter tools to check the language standards and unit tests shall be written for each function block.
- An example shall be published on GitHub with an easy-to-use running option to let the users understand results without going deeper into the algorithm.
- The tool shall be designed with design patterns to be quickly extendable.

2.1.5 Security Measure

Our image quality index does not provide any security concerns. It is an algorithm, an index only, and cannot force security leaches. On the other hand, the tool for testing purposes shall be designed and shared on GitHub with open-source licensing. It does not provide any download and upload from the web and does not open any socket to have a vulnerability. Many contributors or researchers can quickly investigate the security leaches by reviewing the code on GitHub.

Chapter 3

RELATED LITERATURE

According to the research findings, the primary metrics or indices utilized for comparison purposes are SSIM and PSNR [5] [6]. The competitions on super-resolution areas of study, such as CVPR, NTIRE and PIRM, use well-known SSIM and PSNR quality indexes. However, Anwar et al. suggest that there needs to be a new index that is more aligned with human perception and free from pixel-based features [7].

Revisiting the well-proven methods is a necessity before going deeper with frequency-based ones.

Korhonen et al. suggests that the greatest advantage behind the Peak Signal to Noise Ratio is its simplicity [8]. It can be easily calculated from the mean squared error values of the pixels between the images compared. Equation (3.1) shows the simple calculation behind the PSNR metric where max is the maximum possible pixel value in the image.

$$\text{PSNR} = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{max}^2}{\text{MSE}} \right) \quad (3.1)$$

Nilsson et al. points the drawbacks of the Structural Similarity (SSIM) Index in their paper delivered from NVIDIA [9]. They put attention on how SSIM is meaningful on statistical sense but not in human vision perception system. They also argue that the original definition of SSIM has lots of open questions on the implementation level such as color encoding problem. Equation (3.2) describes the relation of the pixel mean and variances on SSIM calculation. μ_x and μ_y are the pixel means of images x and y , σ_x^2 and σ_y^2 are the variances of images x and y , σ_{xy} is the covariance between the images x and y . c values are the coefficients designed to be more stabilized metric.

$$\text{SSIM}(x, y) = \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y + c_1)(2\sigma_{xy} + c_2)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + c_1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + c_2)} \quad (3.2)$$

There are already defined image quality assessment algorithms using the frequency domain instead of the conventional spatial domain.

Narwaria et al. implemented a reduced-reference image quality index that uses a division-to-bins strategy for frequency components where the higher frequencies represent more giant bins than the lower frequencies [10]. They suggest this idea by referencing the human perception system, as it can tolerate more errors on higher frequencies than lower ones. They mentioned that the metrics can be used as both full-reference and reduced-reference, which differs from the other metrics in the area. They argue that the phase component is more vital since it encodes the information related to sharpness and texture changes (like contours) and, therefore, focuses more on the phase part as a primary concern.

Alsaka et al. used a new image quality index for their comparison of hologram regeneration algorithms [11] using frequency domain representations. They divide the Fourier plane into the non-zero intensity value region and the zero intensity value region. These regions are variable according to the input shape's intensities. Afterwards, they compared the non-zero intensity value region with the reference image's same region to present a quality result.

Gunawan et al. introduced a new quality assessment technique based on analyzing the local harmonics of image gradients [12]. They found that comparing the local harmonics of the image gradient between the reference and generated images provides significant information on blurriness. They first calculate the gradient of the images using the 3x3 Sobel operator and apply the 2D Fast Fourier Transform to find the frequency domain representations of each block. Afterwards, they subtract the gains of each harmonic component between the reference and the generated image to create a local harmonic loss. Using an averaging method, they find a scalar value for the image quality index from these block-based local harmonic losses.

There are also many metrics and indexes designed as an artificial intelligence model, such as multi-layer perceptron and deep-neural networks [13] [14] [15]. Although it may be seen as a great improvement over the classical methods, much investigation and research are still needed on the solutions based on artificial intelligence models due to their indeterministic behaviours.

Chapter 4

SYSTEM DESIGN

The proposed comparison index for super-resolution algorithms requires a design process where most of the work would be done in the test and evaluation stages. However, developing an application or a tool that provides the index without additional effort may require system design steps that must be followed. This section will give our design decisions and their underlying reasoning.

4.1 Realistic Constraints and Conditions

The ability to compare images and measure their qualities based on mathematical tools requires a significant amount of time to design, test, and evaluate the results found. As an undergraduate student, being under such a heavy load in a short period, like four months, is seen as the biggest problem. The discussions need to be further employed with the project advisor after the thesis submission, and an extension of the project time seems necessary to create a robust and well-defined comparison index.

Apart from the previous constraint, having a limited number of sources on the image quality indexing techniques under the frequency domain and their usage of the super-resolution techniques brings up problems such as wrong decision-making. These problems would be solved, even if only in part, with the help of advice from different fields on image processing and discussions made with the researchers on the needs of the super-resolution study area.

As the proposed project will be created as an algorithm and a software tool, there will be no harmful or positive effect on environmental and sustainability perspectives. Manufacturability is the key to success when considering the term as "being able to integrate the solution into client problems". We will provide our comparison indexing algorithm

with pseudo-code and Python format to achieve maximum manufacturability. It will allow many users to either implement their code using the specific type of programming style they want or use it directly without going into details with the index algorithm.

For the public health and safety regulations, we do not provide any content that may be restricted or context that can stand as a topic of these laws.

This study's political and social effects can be on the level of academic improvement and are limited to the area of research only.

4.2 Cost of the Design

A software engineering project consists of a development cycle that may or may not introduce additional costs than the labour pays. In our project, we supplied our time as an expense of the suggested comparison index design and used a programming toolset within open-source licensing as much as possible. Therefore, the costs described in this subsection are optional and can be higher or lower without additional difficulties.

As we believe in the power of open-source licensing and libre software principles, we used libre sources in our strategy. However, there are powerful hardware needs in the testing phase of the proposed index due to the complex training operations for super-resolution models. The Holographic Imaging Laboratory's graphical processing units were used to train state-of-the-art artificial intelligence models with the help of Prof. Dr. Gökhan Bora Esmer. Development of the tools is done on our computers simultaneously.

All the components used in the project's development have been summarized with their usage area, expense and specific versions in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Cost of Design

Category	Component	Used Area	Expenses
Scripting Language	Python	To develop the tool for index and train super-resolution models	Free (GNU General Public License compatible Python Software Foundation License)
Development Environment	VSCodium, Debian, pip	To develop the software project	Free (MIT, GNU General Public License v3, MIT)
Version Control System	git, GitHub	To track the version management of the tool and the training scripts of models	Free (GNU General Public License v2), Free (Property Software)
Datasets	DIV2K, Set5	To train the super-resolution, test the proposed index and the tool	Free (Academic research purposes only)
Super-Resolution Models	HAT, Real-ESRGAN	To use for generation test images for the comparison index	Free (Apache-2.0, BSD-3.0-Clause)
Graphics Processing Unit	NVIDIA Tesla V100 from Google Colab	To prepare training codes for the super-resolution models	\$9.90 / month
Graphics Processing Unit	NVIDIA GeForce 1080Ti	To train the images for long-period of times	\$649.00
Development Workstation	Apple Macbook Pro M2 Pro Model MPHE3TU/A	To be used for main development on each part of the study	\$2,450.00

Table 4.1 shows that most of the work has been done with no additional charges on the project. Many other projects have used the hardware setup and will use them afterwards.

4.3 Engineering Standards

We will follow and use several standards defined by institutions, groups and communities during the project development. Standards will be demonstrated in categories of their usage to feed readability with context outline.

4.3.1 Image Standards

Standardization in the image and video industry is essential to provide interchangeability between different environments. As a result, the comparison index tool we design must follow the implementation details of popular image standards such as JPEG, PNG, TIFF. In this part of the study, we will only explore the raster images, which means the 2D matrices with pixels as an image representation style.

Joint Photographic Experts Group (JPEG) is a group that designs a standard lossy image format called JPEG File Interchange Format (JIFF) and published under the ITU-T T.81 specification. It uses 24-bit pixel depth in 3 colour spaces, which results in 256 different shades of each colour space. The advantage of the JPEG over the remaining formats is its data encoding method with Discrete Cosine Transform that allows users to compress an image up to 5% of its initial size [16]. By 2018, it is the most widely used image format around the globe [17]. Super-resolution research is vital to retrieving data from this massive amount of images encoded with lossy image format JPEG.

Portable Network Graphics (PNG) is a lossless image format that provides 24-bit, and 32-bit colour depth depending on the choice of the alpha channel [18]. The alpha channel enables storing transparent images besides the JPEG format. It is published under ISO 15948:2004 standard. It uses chunks to encode the pixel data but also metadata [16]. Users can define a palette of their own within a metadata section and distribute the pixel colour encodings within the palette used.

Tag Image File Format (TIFF) is an image format heavily used in the printing industry. It compresses the images with lossless algorithms. The most significant advantage of the TIFF format is its expandability to different resolutions, image sizes and screens [16]. It uses tags as metadata to encode the information about the details. It is under the development of Adobe Inc. with the specification number ISO 12234-2.

The introduced formats are the three primary image representation containers used in the internet era and our tool will be supporting each of described image standards.

Image quality analysis is another standardization concern, standardized by the International Standards Organization with ISO 19264-1:2021 specification in 2012 [19]. In our proposed method, we will follow their reasoning and implement as much as we can from their experiences.

4.3.2 Coding Standards

Programming in a common manner is compulsory when distributing the source code. It allows the reviewers or the users with coding skills to enhance the code or patch overlooked problems. By following the industry standards on our tool, we endeavour to construct a marketing strategy for our proposed index.

PEP-8 is a style guide standard for the Python programming language that defines the structure of a Python file, the naming conventions and many other parameters usually decided by the programmer. The Python Enhancement Proposals group published the guide in 2001, and now, most Python developers and projects follow the restrictions.

In our project, we have followed the PEP-8 guide and used an autonomous tool to provide feedback on our PEP-8 compliance called as *autopep8*.

Placing helper texts inside the code, known as *comments*, is the other important part of programming project management. It allows newcomers to the project to understand the functionalities of the code blocks. There are plenty of different commenting approaches, but the critical one is explaining the parameters and returns of the project's function units. It can be thought of as placing a small manual after each function block that describes what parameters the function needs and what the output from the function with given parameters will be.

The strategy of placing comments for function block's responsibilities is known as **docstrings**. NumPy, Google and Sphinx are the most common docstring formats. In the tool generation part of our project, we used the Sphinx-formatted docstrings to provide necessary information to the developers and users of the tool.

4.3.3 Project Management Standards

Kanban project management is a graphical and iterative approach to organizing assignments by splitting the whole job into small tasks. The procedure uses visual cards to optimize workflow and improve efficiency. In the context of project management, Kanban provides a real-time, transparent sight of the entire project, allowing stakeholders to track their performance.

The root of Kanban is the board, a visual representation of the project's workflow separated into columns expressing different phases. Tasks are cards that move across these columns from creation to completion. This visual model provides a clear understanding of the assignment in progress, bottlenecks, and the overall flow of tasks.

In our research and development workflow, we have been using the Kanban project management technique to share information on the progress between the group and the adviser. It improves our mentality when dealing with blockages.

In the context of version management, *git* is a distributed version control system developed to track modifications in source code during software development. *git* offers features like tagging for keeping specific points in history, enabling the release of stable versions. The capability to revert to previous states, track changes across branches, and collaborate effectively makes *git* a vital tool for version control.

We have used *git* as our version control manager to track our history within intervals created after feature additions to avoid losing any information on our development cycle. As a hosting platform for our *git* repository, we have used GitHub thanks to their free-of-charge storage possibility.

4.3.4 Super Resolution Models Standards

We have found that a group of scientists organized a standardization group, named as XPixelGroup, in the area of image enhancement. They provided many different super-resolution models with their baseline **BasicSR framework** [20]. It is an open Source image and video restoration toolbox that can be used as a concrete foundation for specific super-resolution algorithm implementations.

The framework allows its users to have the same sense of dataset creation, hyperparameters tuning, model weight results saving and training configuration set-up. The models to be used in the testing phase of our index will be implemented using the BasicSR framework to have a cooperative methodology and decrease the time of work needed.

There are number of ways to store artificial intelligence model weights. These possibilities align with the amount of different machine learning frameworks. In this project, we will be using PyTorch state dictionary object with ending *.pth* to store our experiment and model results. Thanks to the enormous community preserving PyTorch's trust in the research area, it would allow people to use the weights quickly.

4.4 Details of the System Design

The system can be divided into three sub-components. The first component is the tool and the algorithm that resides in the tool. This part of the system provides the users the ability to choose any metric or index they want and pre-processing functions for their input images. It is designed as three different fields of work as shown in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: System Design Overview for the Tool

The tool is responsible for calculating our proposed index, SSIM index, PSNR metric and MSE metric. As a helper functionality, it can downscale or upscale an image given as an input with nearest-neighbour, linear, and bicubic interpolations. We designed the system on top of the OpenCV package to read and write the images and perform basic operations, NumPy for storing and processing the image data and scikit-image to calculate the SSIM, PSNR and MSE. It will provide an API for all these functionality.

The comparison index is designed for super-resolution models. Thus, two or more state-of-the-art super-resolution models are necessary to test our implementation. Different types of artificial intelligence-based super-resolution methods provide different advantages and disadvantages. In this thesis, we wanted to look into two different types of super-resolution models; one of them is a well-accepted GAN-based method named Real-ESRGAN [21], and the other one is a recently developed transformer-based method named HAT-L [1]. Although we did not scrutinize this during the research process, these two articles, co-authored, came from the XPixelGroup team.

Figure 4.2: Comparison Between Real-ESRGAN and HAT Models Results (Reference: [1])

An enhanced super-resolution generative adversarial network (ESRGAN) is a GAN-based method without batch normalization and with dense blocks where each block is connected to the output blocks to allow residual connections [2]. Training the ESRGAN model using real-world images with a variety of objects from nature makes it Real-ESRGAN [22].

Figure 4.3: ESRGAN Architecture (Reference: [2])

The hybrid attention transformer model was created with the question of "Can transformers be better than convolutional neural networks?". The HAT model integrates the channel- and self-attention mechanisms to perform better when using global information

and the latter representativeness [1]. Aside from that, the model uses a technique to overlap the attention cross-sections to achieve more activation of the pixels. This model is presented on the CVPR2023 [3].

Figure 4.4: HAT Architecture (Reference: [3])

To compare the selected models, we decided to use the same dataset with the same amount of training time. The selected dataset is DIV2K since it includes a mixture of different images and is very popular thanks to the CVPR competition [23][24][25][26]. The dataset consists of PNG image formatted files, and the downsampled versions use bicubic downsampling. We have used 60% of the dataset and cropped them into sub-images. Each model is trained using 19545 training images and validated with 2517 images.

Figure 4.5: System Design Overview for Super-Resolution Models Training

As shown in Figure 4.5, we have designed options and metadata files to use the same

configuration and dataset. The BasicSR framework provides a sub-image extraction tool with readers for options and metadata files.

We will obtain the results by comparing our proposed index with proven industry-standard indexes and conducting tests on different scenarios. The scenarios may include the following test cases:

- Comparison between metrics to study the alignment of already standardized methods,
- Image modification-based testing with rotated, mirrored and blacked images to study the performance of the index,
- Comparison between already-known, better-performing super-resolution techniques to study the trueness of the outputs.

Chapter 5

METHODS

We will share the progress of our experimentation on developing the comparison index algorithm, tool, and models training. Each subsection represents a different set of objectives we have defined in Section 2.

5.1 Development of the Comparison Index Algorithm

The Fourier Transform is a mathematical tool used in signal processing. The analysis of the signals is performed on the frequency domain, where the information is represented by frequencies, their power and the phase [27]. It is a fundamental tool to regain information about the patterns of a signal. In the context of image processing, it helps us to discover the higher frequencies where the noise is mainly utilized.

The Fourier of an image can be calculated with Equation (1.1), and its spatial domain can be reverted with Equation (1.2). Note that a Fourier transform can be only calculated on greyscale images if the complex plane is used. Although there are attempts to create a hypercomplex plane to calculate the Fourier transform on colour images, it is beyond our scope [28].

The frequency representation of an image provides us several noteworthy points. Higher frequencies represent rapid changes, such as edges or noises, while lower frequencies represent smooth regions. Having dominant magnitudes on higher frequencies indicates that the image has finer details and dominant magnitudes on lower frequencies distinguish textures, such as in the background. By utilizing the relationship between magnitudes and corresponding frequencies, important image-processing tasks such as edge detection, smoothing, and sharpening can be achieved [29].

Phases of the Fourier components, known as harmonics, represent the relative locations of the peaks of the sine wave. Thus, they are necessary for reconstructing the spatial domain. Different from their importance in reconstruction, they are comparatively unproductive in the analysis of an image. In an image, the magnitudes of the FFT indicate the strength of different frequencies. Meanwhile, the phases encode spatial relationships between these frequencies, which help reconstruct the original image.

We wanted to prepare an index where the structural alignment does not provide any importance, but the structure itself does. Therefore, we selected to continue with magnitudes of the frequency domain in our proposed index to compare images. Having the Fourier Transform applied to the grayscale version of an image also enhances our index's capability to overcome the changes in colour scope since having a better resolution does not have a direct relation with the colour changes.

Super-resolution research focuses on improving performance on high-frequency components since downscaling operations preserve low-frequency details [30]. A high-frequency harmonic encodes the information about the finer structure of the image. Hence, the amount of meaningful harmonics on the higher-frequency zone provides better resolution on the images. However, it should be noted that one picture may have more meaningful harmonics while those elements are all-noise. Consequently, we need to compare the reference image's harmonics with the generated one's to overcome the erroneous judgment of the noise and greater resolution of a different image.

Figure 5.1: The harmonics magnitudes in log scale for two different super-resolution technique and the original.

Figure 5.1 presents the idea we have described. In this experiment, we have used an image of Inci Gürün, known as Inji to calculate frequency domain representations of

original image, bicubic interpolated image with scaling factor of 2, and a super-resolution of a state-of-the-art model from Google researchers [31]. We have applied a filter to remove low amplitude components to show the purpose clearly.

Figure 5.2: The images in spatial domain shown in Figure 5.1.

Figure 5.1 and Figure 5.2 illustrate that having a better resolution aligns with being similar. This similarity can be degraded into two main components: the structural similarity and the diameter of scattering in magnitudes.

In our comparison index, we will be calculating the radius of the structurally similar sub-part of the Fourier magnitudes by starting from the outer circle and getting smaller into the Fourier's DC component. Due to the difficulty of representing circles on computer graphics, we will be implementing our decreasing area method using squares. The area of interest will start with the half size of the whole image Fourier magnitudes and decrease by 2 pixels on each axis until the 5x5 pixel Fourier magnitudes.

Figure 5.3: The decreasing grid size used for comparison.

On each area of interest, we will be calculating the SSIM of the Fourier magnitudes of the original image and the upscaled. Until the point of success, which is defined by a

parameter utilized on the index, the loop continues. The SSIM index is used since it is the most efficient way of comparing structural information. The scikit-image package is used for SSIM calculations.

The algorithm in pseudo-code format can be found on Algorithm 1. An implementation of the algorithm in Python can be found in Appendix A.3.

The proposed performance index output is calibrated to be a percentage of the radius of its harmonically akin area to reference image's width, aligning with the radius term. This *radius* quantifies the extent of similarity in harmonic content and is expressed in pixel units, where each pixel represents a frequency component. Given that the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) of an image mirrors the spatial domain's size, the highest attainable value of the proposed index is 100%. Conversely, its minimum value is zero, as the radius can only be defined as natural numbers. Thus, the proposed performance index can be defined within the range of $[0, 100]$, offering a standardized measure for comparing single super-resolution models based on image sizes.

5.2 Development of the Tool

The tool is necessary to calculate and make experiments within the proposed comparison index. Besides, a tool will create an easier-to-use interface for the super-resolution model developers. Thus, we have designed our tool to be as modular as possible and with an architecture-first approach. We have followed the SOLID principles while designing the software architecture.

- **Single Responsibility:** A class only carries one dedicated functionality, which means that there would be only one reason to change.
- **Open/Closed Principle:** Any addition or removal of an element from a class would not break anything in the codebase.
- **Liskov Substitution:** A child class must inherit all the functionality from its parent class.
- **Interface Segregation:** A class must be provided with its client interface within an application to overcome the issue of functionality change.
- **Dependency Inversion:** A change in the subclass would not create a need for change in its parent class.

Algorithm 1 The Comparison Index Algorithm

Require: SUCCESS_THRESH

```
1: function harmonic_radius:
2:   fft_true  $\leftarrow$  fft_log_mag(y_true)
3:   fft_pred  $\leftarrow$  fft_log_mag(y_pred)
4:
5:   center_width  $\leftarrow$  dims(fft_true, 0) // 2
6:   center_height  $\leftarrow$  dims(fft_true, 1) // 2
7:
8:   grid_size  $\leftarrow$  smallest_side_size(fft_true)
9:
10:  while 1 do
11:
12:    width_start  $\leftarrow$  center_width - grid_size // 2
13:    width_end  $\leftarrow$  center_width + grid_size // 2
14:    height_start  $\leftarrow$  center_height - grid_size // 2
15:    height_end  $\leftarrow$  center_height + grid_size // 2
16:
17:    grid_pred  $\leftarrow$  fft_pred[width_start:width_end, height_start:height_end]
18:    grid_true  $\leftarrow$  fft_true[width_start:width_end, height_start:height_end]
19:
20:    ssim_result  $\leftarrow$  SSIM(grid_true, grid_pred, 0, 255)
21:
22:    if ssim_result  $\geq$  SUCCESS_THRESH then
23:      found_radius  $\leftarrow$  grid_size
24:      image_radius  $\leftarrow$  smallest_side_size(fft_true)
25:      return (found_radius / image_radius) * 100
26:    end if
27:
28:    grid_size  $\leftarrow$  grid_size - 2
29:
30:    if grid_size  $\leq$  7 then
31:      break
32:    end if
33:  end while
34:
35:  radius  $\leftarrow$  0
36:  return radius
```

In software engineering design, the design patterns deliver the SOLID principles with high reliability, proven by their use in the field. We have used Strategy Pattern to implement different metrics and interfaces and a mediator pattern to perform as a coordinator between the functionalities.

Figure 5.4 shows the components of the system with their interfaces. *SRAnalyzer* is the main component that works as a **mediator pattern** between different parts of the program. A *SRAnalyzer* might have multiple numbers of images and metrics with one reference image. A metric is defined with an interface of *InterfaceMetric* and provides a simple function, called *calculate()*. This connection between implemented indexes/ metrics, *InterfaceMetric* and *SRAnalyzer* is implemented with **strategy pattern**.

A *SRAnalyzer* may or may not have different *Images* that encapsulates the functionality of an image. Each *Image* instance can be assigned to a *Preprocessor* which provides pre-processing operations such as downscaling and upscaling. Within this structure, any additional metric, index, upscaler, downscaler or any preprocessor can be easily added without breaking the remaining of the code.

Figure 5.4: The UML diagram of the tool architecture.

Besides the defined architecture, we have provided a couple of utility functions to increase the user’s efficiency. The usage of the API, Application Programming Interface, and the main experimental setup for the thesis is shown in the code in Appendix A.4.

We will use this provided tool to experiment on the proposed index.

5.3 Training HAT and Real-ESRGAN Models

Using only one approach to train different super-resolution models can be achieved by using the BasicSR framework [20]. The framework provides an Apache-2.0 licensed API to super-resolution developers with many functionalities encapsulated inside their codebase. As a developer, the sole responsibility becomes designing and implementing the architecture after the framework's contributions.

Although the lack of documentation creates certain difficulties for developers, it is easy to form an idea by examining the code of many models they have implemented. For the HAT model, they have released the model with training documentation to us through a repository on GitHub. For the Real-ESRGAN model, a developer from the community created a test and training repository using the BasicSR framework.

Figure 5.5: The overview of the DIV2K dataset.

We have followed documentations and prepared two different Python Jupyter Notebooks. As a first step, we downloaded the whole DIV2K dataset and generated sub-images of 400x400 from two times downsampled versions and original high-resolution versions. It increased the number of training images to 49,080 and validation images to 6,240.

Afterwards, we implemented a script to select 40% of the dataset randomly. The selection reduced the number of images, hence decreasing the time consumption of the training processes. Also, a random selection of the dataset removed the bias of the DIV2K dataset as much as possible.

The cropped sub-images are saved into the file system and paired as high-resolution and their corresponding low-resolutions in a meta-data file. A common metadata file is critical in our experiments since we want to reduce the effect of the training set. Up to this point, the stages were typical in two models thanks to the BasicSR framework. The metadata file has paired 19545 images for training and 2517 images for validation.

Options files are the parameters that model training needs, such as input dataset, optimizer settings, validation settings and many more. Each model may have its own options. Nevertheless, a standard option file is mainly distributed with the model to copy. We have used the options files provided and inserted our metadata files as training and validation datasets.

Another critical point for our experiments is training the models in the same amount of time. It would allow us to compare not just their results but their performances. To achieve the objective, we have tried 12500 iterations on the HAT model and 50000 iterations on Real-ESRGAN with 50000 iterations on Real-ESRNet, the discriminator of the GAN. This training has been done on NVIDIA GeForce 1080Ti and roughly consumed 12 hours for each.

Figure 5.6: x2 Upscaled Model Results on a Baby Photo from the Set5.

The workflow of training and inferencing super-resolution models using BasicSR framework is illustrated in Figure A.1 in Appendix A.5.

5.4 Continues Integration and Continues Deployment

To ensure the reliability, maintainability, and accessibility of our super-resolution model comparison index, we have implemented a robust Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipeline using GitHub Actions. This automated workflow streamlines the development process, allowing for seamless integration of code changes, rigorous testing, and effortless distribution of our index.

5.4.1 Continuous Integration

The Continuous Integration component of our pipeline focuses on the automatic verification of code quality and functionality upon every update. When a contributor submits a change (e.g., a bug fix or a new feature), the following steps are automatically triggered:

- **Code Formatting Check (flake8):** This tool ensures adherence to the PEP 8 style guide, which is a set of conventions for writing Python code. This step helps maintain code readability and consistency.
- **Static Code Analysis (pylint):** Pylint performs a deeper analysis of the codebase, identifying potential errors, bugs, and areas for improvement. It helps catch issues early in the development cycle.
- **Unit Testing and Coverage (pytest-coverage):** PyTest-Cov executes a suite of unit tests that verify the individual components of our index. Additionally, it measures code coverage, indicating the percentage of code that is actually tested. We aim for 100% code coverage to guarantee thorough testing.

By automating these checks, we ensure that every contribution meets our quality standards before it is integrated into the main codebase. This significantly reduces the likelihood of introducing errors or regressions. The automation script is seen in the code A.1.

5.4.1.1 Unit Testing

Unit testing is a software development practice that focuses on verifying the smallest testable components of an application, such as individual functions or methods, in isolation. It aims to ensure that each unit performs as expected independently of other parts of the system. In our project, we have adopted a comprehensive unit testing approach to ensure the reliability and correctness of our index.

There are generally three types of testing methods available. Unit testing is described above, it focuses on testing individual units of code in isolation. Integration testing examines the interactions between different units or components of the system to ensure they work together correctly. Lastly, system testing assesses the complete, integrated system to verify that it meets the specified requirements.

While integration and system testing are valuable for evaluating the overall functionality of a software system, we have prioritized unit testing in our project due to the following reasons:

- **Modularity:** Our index is designed with a modular architecture, making it well-suited for unit testing.
- **Early Bug Detection:** Unit tests help identify errors early in the development cycle, making them easier and less expensive to fix.
- **Refactoring Confidence:** With a comprehensive suite of unit tests, we can confidently refactor our code without fear of introducing unintended consequences.

To ensure that our unit tests cover all aspects of our index's functionality, we have achieved 100% code coverage. This means that every line of code in our index is executed by at least one unit test. To isolate the behavior of our index from external dependencies, we have utilized mocking techniques. Mocking involves creating simulated versions of external components, allowing us to test our index in a controlled environment without relying on the actual implementation of those components.

By prioritizing unit testing and achieving 100% code coverage, we have established a solid foundation for the reliability and maintainability of our super-resolution model comparison index. This rigorous testing approach ensures that our index is a trustworthy tool for researchers and practitioners in the field of image processing.

5.4.2 Continuous Deployment

The Continuous Deployment component of our pipeline facilitates the automatic release and distribution of our index to the Python Package Index (PyPI). When a new version is ready for release, the following actions are taken:

- **Package Building:** The code is packaged into a format suitable for distribution.

- **Package Upload (PyPI):** The package is uploaded to PyPI, making it available to users worldwide.
- **Tool Upload (PyPI):** Any associated tools or scripts are also uploaded to PyPI, providing a convenient way for users to access and utilize them.

Once these steps are completed, users can easily install our index and its tools using a simple command: `pip install harmonicsradius`. This streamlined distribution process ensures that the latest version of our index is readily accessible to the research community. The automation script is in the code A.2.

5.4.3 Advantages of CI/CD

The implementation of a CI/CD pipeline offers numerous benefits to both developers and users:

- **Faster Development Cycles:** By automating testing and deployment, we can iterate more quickly and release updates more frequently.
- **Improved Code Quality:** Automated checks help identify and fix issues early, leading to more reliable and robust code.
- **Reduced Manual Effort:** Developers can focus on writing code rather than spending time on repetitive tasks like testing and deployment.
- **Increased Accessibility:** Automatic publishing to PyPI makes our index readily available to a wider audience.
- **Enhanced Collaboration:** The streamlined workflow encourages contributions from other researchers and developers.

Overall, our CI/CD pipeline plays a crucial role in ensuring the quality, reliability, and accessibility of our super-resolution model comparison index, making it a valuable tool for researchers and practitioners in the field of image processing.

Chapter 6

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed comparison index for super-resolution models is tested and evaluated with regard to different scenarios. In this section, the results of different experiments are supplied, and their outcomes are examined.

6.1 Simulations and Testing

An *index* is a critical point that must be robust, efficient and trustworthy. Since we designed our proposed method for comparison of the super-resolution models as an image quality index, we need to perform several simulations and tests to have a concrete understanding of its implementation. Thus, this subsection will investigate answers to four questions, which are listed in the following items.

1. Does the index *really* distinguish a high-resolution image from a low-resolution one?
2. Does the index align with the metrics or indexes in the area of study? If not, how so?
3. Does the index follow the requirement of *minimally* influenced by the spatial domain-based structural changes?
4. Does the index calculate the results *fast* to be used for video processing?

To understand the first question, we will be using two strategies: using the index on a comparison of bicubic and linear interpolated images and on two super-resolution models where the results can be easily classified as high- and low-resolution by human vision.

The second question may not give us a complete idea of the robustness; however, inspecting the relation between different metrics and indexes creates additional information

on improving our index. Therefore, we will compare the indexes and provide a context to the reader.

We want to see the limits of the index by answering the third question with a couple of experiments. These experiments will implement a colour change, a mirroring and a partly blocked image to understand the performance of the index under harsh conditions. The last question will guide us about the possibility of using this metric for video super resolution.

Note that HRI95 represents the proposed index with success threshold as 0.95 described in Algorithm 1.

6.1.1 Comparison of the Results of Linear and Bicubic Interpolations

We have used the Set5 dataset to upscale them by scale factors 2 and 4 and calculated the proposed index results. Table 6.1 shows us that our index compares a bicubic and linear image correctly since bicubic interpolation calculates the new pixels from surrounding 16 pixels whereas linear interpolation uses 2 pixels. Also, having the x4 results lower than the x2 scaled results aligns with the mathematics.

Table 6.1: Results of the Index on Bicubic and Linear Upscaling

Image	Upscaler	Scale Factor	Index Result (HRI95)
Baby Image	Linear Interpolation	x2	41.797%
Baby Image	Bicubic Interpolation	x2	43.750%
Baby Image	Linear Interpolation	x4	22.266%
Baby Image	Bicubic Interpolation	x4	23.047%
Parrot Image	Linear Interpolation	x2	40.278%
Parrot Image	Bicubic Interpolation	x2	45.139%
Parrot Image	Linear Interpolation	x4	21.528%
Parrot Image	Bicubic Interpolation	x4	22.917%
Butterfly Image	Linear Interpolation	x2	42.188%
Butterfly Image	Bicubic Interpolation	x2	44.531%
Butterfly Image	Linear Interpolation	x4	21.875%
Butterfly Image	Bicubic Interpolation	x4	22.656%
Boy Image	Linear Interpolation	x2	41.429%
Boy Image	Bicubic Interpolation	x2	43.571%
Boy Image	Linear Interpolation	x4	20.714%
Boy Image	Bicubic Interpolation	x4	22.143%
Woman Image	Linear Interpolation	x2	47.368%
Woman Image	Bicubic Interpolation	x2	49.123%
Woman Image	Linear Interpolation	x4	23.684%
Woman Image	Bicubic Interpolation	x4	25.439%

Figure 6.1 shows the baby image and butterfly image with their harmonics radius found.

Figure 6.1: The image (a) shows a linearly 2x interpolated image, and the image (e) presents its harmonic radius index in frequency domain magnitudes. The image (b) shows a 2x bicubic interpolation on the same image, and the image (f) presents its harmonic radius index in frequency domain magnitudes. In the last two columns, image (c) represents a 4x linearly interpolated image and image (d) shows a 4x bicubic interpolated image with their harmonic radius indexes respectively in (g) and (h).

6.1.2 Comparison of the Results of Super-Resolution Models

We have used the Set5 dataset to upscale them by scale factor 2 using trained HAT and Real-ESRGAN models. Table 6.2 shows the results of each image in the dataset using the proposed index.

As shown in Figure 6.2 and Figure 6.3, the proposed index has found a significant difference between Real-ESRGAN and HAT-L models — the lack of finer details on Real-ESRGAN results in lower magnitudes on the higher frequencies. Thus, our proposed index found a vast difference between the models. It helps the super-resolution developers to have a better-scaled index to fine-tune their models.

Table 6.2: Results of the Index on Bicubic and Linear Upscaling

Image	Upscaler	Scale Factor	Index Result (HRI95)
Baby Image	Real-ESRGAN Model	x2	15.625%
Baby Image	HAT Model	x2	45.312%
Parrot Image	Real-ESRGAN Model	x2	18.750%
Parrot Image	HAT Model	x2	50.000%
Butterfly Image	Real-ESRGAN Model	x2	25.781%
Butterfly Image	HAT Model	x2	52.344%
Boy Image	Real-ESRGAN Model	x2	15.714%
Boy Image	HAT Model	x2	45.000%
Woman Image	Real-ESRGAN Model	x2	25.439%
Woman Image	HAT Model	x2	55.263%

6.1.3 Coherence with Other Indexes and Metrics

Although the proposed comparison index does not use the spatial domain in its algorithm, it considers the spatial domain when calculating the result. A transformation might change the space we are working on; however, the space still encodes the information related to the previous one. Therefore, we expect the proposed index to be *somehow* aligned with the spatial domain indexes such as SSIM, PSNR, and MSE.

In this experiment, we calculated the chosen indexes on all of the Set5 data. To create a wholesome picture, we compared all the upscaling methods we have designed.

Table 6.3: Results of the Indexes with All Upscalers on Baby Image

Upscaler	MSE	PSNR	SSIM	HRI95
Nearest Neighbour Interpolation	34.66 px^2	32.73 dB	0.9269	43.75%
Linear Interpolation	24.06 px^2	34.32 dB	0.9338	41.80%
Bicubic Interpolation	16.92 px^2	35.85 dB	0.9532	43.75%
Real-ESRGAN Model	154.8 px^2	26.23 dB	0.8005	15.63%
HAT Model	12.47 px^2	37.17 dB	0.9650	45.31%

Table 6.4: Results of the Indexes with All Upscalers on Parrot Image

Upscaler	MSE	PSNR	SSIM	HRI95
Nearest Neighbour Interpolation	56.24 px^2	30.63 dB	0.9347	45.14%
Linear Interpolation	33.33 px^2	32.90 dB	0.9527	40.28%
Bicubic Interpolation	19.09 px^2	35.32 dB	0.9699	45.14%
Real-ESRGAN Model	174.27 px^2	25.72 dB	0.7716	18.75%
HAT Model	7.866 px^2	39.17 dB	0.99816	50.00%

Figure 6.2: Comparison of Parrot Image’s Real-ESRGAN and HAT models and their harmonics radius.

Table 6.5: Results of the Indexes with All Upscalers on Butterfly Image

Upscaler	MSE	PSNR	SSIM	HRI95
Nearest Neighbour Interpolation	288.2 px^2	23.43 dB	0.8659	44.53%
Linear Interpolation	220.6 px^2	24.59 dB	0.8738	42.19%
Bicubic Interpolation	148.2 px^2	26.32 dB	0.9047	44.53%
Real-ESRGAN Model	364.2 px^2	22.41 dB	0.8061	25.78%
HAT Model	36.41 px^2	32.42 dB	0.9664	52.34%

The outcomes indicate that the proposed index does align with the previous indexes and metrics. It has been verified that it can catch the Real-ESRGAN’s low interpretation due to it being underfitted.

6.1.4 Results of Spatial Domain Modifications

The question “Does the index follow the requirement of minimally influenced by the spatial domain-based structural changes?” is answered in this section by conducting three experiments where the spatial domain of the image is subjected to modifications.

Figure 6.3: Comparison of Boy Image’s Real-ESRGAN and HAT models and their harmonics radius.

- We changed the colours of a comparingly high-resolution image and compared it with the exact coloured low-resolution image.
- We applied mirroring effects to a comparingly high-resolution image and compared it with a truly aligned low-resolution image.
- We placed black areas on top of the high-resolution image and compared it with a typical low-resolution image.

We have applied a colour change on a HAT model generated image and used its linear interpolation version to compare them with SSIM and the proposed index. Figure 6.4 shows the differences in the images in the spatial domain.

Table 6.8 proves that the proposed method can detect high-resolution images better than Structural Similarity (SSIM) Index when there is an color deformation.

A mirroring operation on both the X and Y axes on a HAT model-generated image is performed, and its linear interpolation version is compared with SSIM and the proposed

Table 6.6: Results of the Indexes with All Upscalers on Boy Image

Upscaler	MSE	PSNR	SSIM	HRI95
Nearest Neighbour Interpolation	56.23 px^2	30.42 dB	0.8034	43.57%
Linear Interpolation	52.21 px^2	30.75 dB	0.7933	41.43%
Bicubic Interpolation	44.82 px^2	31.41 dB	0.8221	43.57%
Real-ESRGAN Model	99.71 px^2	27.94 dB	0.6601	15.71%
HAT Model	39.31 px^2	31.98 dB	0.8447	45.00%

Table 6.7: Results of the Indexes with All Upscalers on Woman Image

Upscaler	MSE	PSNR	SSIM	HRI95
Nearest Neighbour Interpolation	106.5 px^2	27.86 dB	0.9222	50.00%
Linear Interpolation	76.95 px^2	29.27 dB	0.9312	47.36%
Bicubic Interpolation	49.80 px^2	31.16 dB	0.9511	49.12%
Real-ESRGAN Model	194.0 px^2	25.25 dB	0.8530	25.44%
HAT Model	22.70 px^2	34.57 dB	0.9728	55.26%

index. Figure 6.5 shows the difference in the images in the spatial domain.

Table 6.9 shows that when an unalignment occurs in the spatial domain of the image, the resulting SSIM scores are critically low. Within our proposed index, the Harmonics Radius Index, we could detect the super-resolution even if there is an alignment issue.

Additionally, we have conducted experiments by applying shifts and listing their SSIM and proposed index results differences. The results can be seen in Table 6.10.

Our last modification is having blacked regions on the image to lose some of its details. The nature of the proposed metric relies on whole images instead of statistical details. Thus, the results shown in Table 6.11 follow the "whole-picture" idea but set a big drawback on the index itself.

It should be remarked that improving the proposed index with additional similarity checks on phase components would be beneficial for such modifications.

6.1.5 Assessment of Channel Importance

In this study, a Bicubic Upscaler algorithm was employed to generate an image. Subsequently, both the generated image and a reference image were decomposed into their respective YUV, HSV, and RGB color components. A comparative analysis of each component pair was conducted utilizing both the Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) and the HRI95 index to assess the perceptual quality and similarity of the generated image in

Figure 6.4: Color Modification in Spatial Domain

Table 6.8: SSIM and The Proposed Index Performance on Color Corruption

Upscaler	SSIM	HRI95
Linear Interpolation	0.9312	47.368%
HAT Model	0.8589	54.386%

relation to the reference image. Within this experiment, we investigate the relative significance of each channel within our proposed index and assess its comparative performance against a channel-specific SSIM analysis. Experiment results can be seen at Tables 6.12, 6.14 and 6.16.

Our experimental analysis revealed noteworthy differences between the novel HRI95 index and the established SSIM metric. Across diverse color spaces and images, these metrics frequently diverged, suggesting a focus on distinct aspects of image quality. This implies that HRI95 could effectively complement SSIM, providing a more comprehensive assessment of super-resolved image fidelity.

HRI95, grounded in sophisticated harmonic analysis and frequency pattern comparison, offers a unique perspective. It thoroughly examines the frequency domain, meticulously comparing reference and super-resolved image details. This involves analyzing the log-magnitude representation of the Fourier transform and comparing frequency patterns within a grid. Notably, SSIM is integrated within this grid to pinpoint regions with matching harmonic patterns, enhancing the index's precision.

A closer examination of the results reveals HRI95's exceptional sensitivity to color

Figure 6.5: Alignment Modification in Spatial Domain

Table 6.9: SSIM and The Proposed Index Performance on Alignment Corruption

Upscaler	SSIM	HRI95
Linear Interpolation	0.9312	47.368%
HAT Model	0.1947	55.263%

distortions, particularly those affecting hue. This sensitivity is pronounced in YUV and HSV color spaces, where HRI95 scores are markedly lower for chrominance channels compared to luma channels. This characteristic could prove invaluable for assessing the preservation of fine details and textures, often associated with high-frequency content.

However, this heightened sensitivity also presents certain limitations. The index may exhibit an excessive response to minor hue shifts, as observed in the HSV color space. Additionally, the absolute HRI95 values may lack the intuitive interpretability of SSIM’s 0 to 1 range. Nevertheless, HRI95’s emphasis on frequency-domain characteristics and color information establishes it as a valuable asset within the image quality assessment toolkit.

6.1.6 Proposed Index Implementing with Sub-Frequency Weights

The proposed performance index evaluates the structural similarity between the Fourier domains of reference and upscaled images. The evaluation commences at the highest frequency components and progresses iteratively towards lower frequencies until a structural similarity index measure (SSIM) score of 0.95 is achieved. This approach ensures that the images are treated as unified entities during comparison.

Figure 6.6: The shifting comparison experiments are conducted by selecting the reference image from the left-top corner and shifting the selected image horizontally from the right side until the end of the image. This process is repeated for various shift amounts. Images on (a), (b), (c), (d) shifted by 11px, 8px, 5px, and 2px respectively.

Table 6.10: SSIM and The Proposed Index Performance on Shift Corruption

Shift Amount	4%	3%	2%	1%
HRI95 Normal	100%	100%	100%	100%
HRI95 Shifted	7.581%	8.571%	10.954%	33.566%
SSIM Normal	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
SSIM Shifted	0.255	0.278	0.371	0.687

Figure 6.7: Blacked Region Modification in Spatial Domain

The algorithm allows for the manipulation of the importance of individual frequency ranges, enabling a fine-grained assessment of the upscaled image quality. In the present study, the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) was segmented into distinct sub-frequency ranges, each of which was assessed using the proposed index. Subsequently, a weighted sum of the index results across all sub-frequency ranges was computed, normalized by the number of sub-frequency bins. This approach demonstrated the flexibility of the proposed index, as it can be readily adapted to emphasize high or low-frequency components or to apply a band-pass filter for a specific frequency range.

As one can see from the Figure 6.8, sub-frequencies are divided into 49 bins. The first bin is the top-left frequency range, and the the last bin is the bottom-right frequency range. On each step, the traversal algorithm shifts half of the bin width or height that allows us to capture DC components as is.

The metrics HRI95 and SSIM were computed for each frequency bin, with results

Table 6.11: SSIM and The Proposed Index Performance on Blacked Region Corruption

Upscaler	SSIM	HRI95
Linear Interpolation	0.9312	47.368%
HAT Model	0.8957	0%

Table 6.12: HRI95 Values for Various Images in YUV Channels

Image	Y Channel	U Channel	V Channel	Mean	HRI95 (Whole Image)
Baby	43.36%	28.52%	28.52%	33.46%	43.75%
Parrot	45.14%	40.97%	39.58%	41.90%	45.14%
Butterfly	44.53%	35.16%	35.16%	38.28%	44.53%
Boy	42.86%	24.29%	33.57%	33.57%	43.57%
Woman	49.12%	26.32%	32.46%	35.97%	49.12%

presented in Table 6.18. Notably, bins 25 and 26, representing the DC component and its adjacent frequencies, exhibit peak HRI95 and SSIM scores. This indicates the superior efficacy of the HAT super-resolution model in capturing low-frequency components. Conversely, higher frequency performance demonstrates significant range-dependency. The bin-based HRI95 methodology offers a nuanced approach to discerning the specific characteristics of diverse super-resolution models.

6.1.7 Frame Rate Calculations

We prepared a program to calculate the frames per second using 500 trials for each upscaling method on each image. It means that from 12500 different images, the frame rate was found to be 30.44 FPS overall. However, it shall be noted that a frame can be computer faster if it is a better resolution image since the calculation starts from the outermost circle.

6.2 Simulation Results

It is shown that the proposed comparison index for super-resolution techniques can be an alternative to SSIM usage in the state-of-the-art or will be a helper in understanding the model results. It has convenient advantages over SSIM and PSNR thanks to decreased interaction with the spatial domain.

The index uses SSIM to compare the harmonics' amplitudes, therefore creating a solid foundation for the reliability of usage in the research. Performing a structure analysis on

Table 6.13: SSIM Values for Various Images in YUV Channels

Image	Y Channel	U Channel	V Channel	Mean	SSIM (Whole Image)
Baby	0.957	0.943	0.967	0.956	0.953
Parrot	0.974	0.981	0.982	0.979	0.967
Butterfly	0.907	0.968	0.956	0.944	0.905
Boy	0.861	0.688	0.754	0.768	0.951
Woman	0.949	0.949	0.976	0.958	0.973

Table 6.14: HRI95 Values for Various Images in HSV Channels

Image	H Channel	S Channel	V Channel	Mean	HRI95 (Whole Image)
Baby	7.422%	7.812%	43.36%	19.53%	43.75%
Parrot	10.42%	20.83%	42.36%	24.54%	45.14%
Butterfly	21.09%	20.31%	43.75%	28.38%	44.53%
Boy	0%	10.00%	42.86%	17.62%	43.57%
Woman	14.91%	29.83%	49.12%	31.29%	49.12%

harmonics needs a parameter of success that is defined with the proposed index and must be indicated when using its results such as HRI95 or HRI85.

It shows that the index is well-forming in its HRI95 form and brings advantages in comparing high-resolution images that have spatial distortions such as colour changes and alignment issues. There might need to be an improvement in the resolution calculation of blacked regions with phase components. Thus, this index paves the way for future research.

Algorithmically, starting from the half of the outermost circle carries an issue of not detecting resolutions more excellent than the half of the Fourier image. During our research, we also conducted the index algorithm by selecting directly the outermost circle, but it created additional complexity for the algorithm. Due to time limitations, we had to select not the best but the functional approach.

The variable index results based on the image shape form a drawback. Each image would have its index scaling, and one index result from an image with another index result from a completely different image should not be compared with each other. It means that an image with a lower HRI95 score might have better resolution than an image with a higher HRI95 score. The described problem might be solved by dividing the number of HRI95 scores by the Fourier representation image size to tighten the scale into the $[0, 0.5]$ range.

The frame rate of the algorithm makes it capable of processing the videos in real-time since the cinematic and video frame rate standards are 25 FPS and 30 FPS. As additional research, a model can be validated using a cost function that includes both SSIM and

Table 6.15: SSIM Values for Various Images in HSV Channels

Image	H Channel	S Channel	V Channel	Mean	SSIM (Whole Image)
Baby	0.915	0.916	0.958	0.930	0.953
Parrot	0.934	0.889	0.975	0.933	0.967
Butterfly	0.957	0.794	0.914	0.888	0.905
Boy	0.388	0.490	0.811	0.563	0.951
Woman	0.896	0.923	0.948	0.922	0.973

Table 6.16: HRI95 Values for Various Images in RGB Channels

Image	R Channel	G Channel	B Channel	Mean	HRI95 (Whole Image)
Baby	43.75%	43.75%	43.75%	43.75%	43.75%
Parrot	44.44%	45.14%	43.75%	44.44%	45.14%
Butterfly	43.75%	44.53%	43.75%	44.01%	44.53%
Boy	43.57%	42.86%	42.86%	43.10%	43.57%
Woman	49.12%	49.12%	49.12%	49.12%	49.12%

HRI95. Experimenting with such a validation cost function would produce a significant performance test on the index.

6.2.1 Strengths and Weaknesses

The strengths of the proposed comparison index are listed in the following element.

- The index uses the information of positive relevance between harmonics count and their structure and the resolution.
- The index overcomes the problems of spatial domain indexes or matrices, such as colour change, image alignment, and pixel shifts.
- The index symbolizes the whole image instead of its statistical components.
- The index creates a better scaling for more outstanding super-resolution research since the SSIM index is stuck between 0.90 and 1.0 due to the state-of-the-art creating magnificent results.
- It can be calculated in real-time for video-processing applications.

On the other hand, the proposed comparison index introduces several weaknesses that leave the door open for future research.

Table 6.17: SSIM Values for Various Images in RGB Channels

Image	R Channel	G Channel	B Channel	Mean	SSIM (Whole Image)
Baby	0.958	0.957	0.944	0.953	0.953
Parrot	0.975	0.974	0.960	0.970	0.967
Butterfly	0.914	0.909	0.878	0.900	0.905
Boy	0.800	0.853	0.811	0.821	0.951
Woman	0.948	0.949	0.948	0.948	0.973

Table 6.18: Sub-Frequency Bin Results

Bin No.	HRI95 (%)	SSIM	Bin No.	HRI95 (%)	SSIM	Bin No.	HRI95 (%)	SSIM
1	0.00	0.07	18	96.88	0.95	35	0.00	0.12
2	0.00	0.10	19	73.44	0.90	36	0.00	0.07
3	0.00	0.17	20	0.00	0.50	37	0.00	0.28
4	0.00	0.25	21	0.00	0.12	38	0.00	0.51
5	0.00	0.17	22	0.00	0.13	39	0.00	0.59
6	0.00	0.10	23	0.00	0.53	40	0.00	0.50
7	0.00	0.08	24	96.88	0.95	41	0.00	0.28
8	0.00	0.09	25	100.00	1.00	42	0.00	0.09
9	0.00	0.27	26	100.00	0.95	43	0.00	0.08
10	0.00	0.48	27	0.00	0.54	44	0.00	0.10
11	0.00	0.58	28	0.00	0.13	45	0.00	0.15
12	0.00	0.51	29	0.00	0.11	46	0.00	0.26
13	0.00	0.28	30	0.00	0.50	47	0.00	0.19
14	0.00	0.07	31	73.44	0.90	48	0.00	0.10
15	0.00	0.11	32	100.00	0.95	49	0.00	0.07
16	0.00	0.48	33	73.44	0.90			
17	70.31	0.88	34	0.00	0.49			

- The index does not perform well if some parts of the image are removed.
- The index algorithm needs to be refined by starting from the outermost circle instead of its half.
- The indexing algorithm does not provide a global scale that can be used to compare two different images with each other.

Chapter 7

CONCLUSION

We designed a comparison index based on the harmonics of the images for super-resolution research and provided a tool to calculate the index. In this section, we summarized our work and presented the impact on the research field.

7.1 Conclusion

Super-resolution research became increasingly famous after significant improvements in artificial intelligence. The state-of-the-art techniques provide great advantages in high-resolution video streaming, image enhancement on microscopy, and many computer vision tasks.

The field of increasing the resolution of the images is heavily dependent on image quality research. This research area provides mathematical tools for measuring an image's quality based on different parameters. The questions of "*How to represent the quality?*" and "*What are the limits of improving the quality?*" is still looking for answers.

With this thesis, we proposed an image quality comparison method using the harmonics to provide a full-reference index for the super-resolution research. The proposed comparison index for the super-resolution models calculates the similarity between the harmonics magnitudes of the reference image and the super-resolution generated image.

The index creates a radius-based result where the higher results represent better resolutions. Due to current implementations being heavily dependent on spatial features, they may not provide accurate comparisons of the patterns of the image. Our proposed index solves the problem of being easily confused of the current indexes by having slight modifications on the image, such as colour change, scene alignment and cumulative pixel shifts.

We have divided the plan of creating a new index based on harmonics analysis into eight objectives, primarily containing constructing the algorithm, programming an open-source tool for it, and performing system-level tests to enhance the capability and see the limits. By the end of the thesis document, we have provided detailed explanations of system design and reasons for algorithmic decisions.

The proposed comparison index's algorithm is defined using the pseudo-code to reach more researchers and has been distributed within a Python API on GitHub¹ to decrease the complexity of implementation.

The experiments showed that our index results were significantly better than SSIM on comparison of the images with spatial modifications such as colour changes and alignment issues. Apart from the corrupted images, the index performed well in comparing the images with different interpolation and super-resolution techniques. Its results are aligned with SSIM and PSNR indexes and introduced an advantage of more reasonable scaling on better-predicted images than the worse-predicted ones over the drawback of SSIM where the results are tied up into the range 0.9 to 1.0 after the artificial intelligence's increasing performances.

The proposed index preserves several weaknesses, such as low performance on images with removed parts and the localness of its results. Since the index makes calculations over the existence of patterns, the removal of the parts on the image creates a considerable change in the search for similarity in harmonics magnitudes. Also, the calculated radius values are based on images and should not be compared with the other images for the comparison of the resolution. An image with better resolution might have a lower harmonics radius score than another image with low resolution.

We believe that the super-resolution research would have a substantial impact after the usage of validation cost functions based on the proposed comparison index. It will help the researcher to understand the slight differences in the state-of-the-art super-resolution model outputs.

¹The repository on GitHub can be found in the following link: <https://github.com/electricalgorithm/harmonics-radius-index>. It is licensed under GPL-3.0

7.2 Future Recommendation

A cost function that includes both the proposed index and a statistics-based method may add a massive impact on the state-of-the-art super-resolution model development. It can reduce the disadvantages for each by using the advantages of other index.

The usage of the proposed comparison index is wider than the image super-resolution area. It could be implemented on a real-time video processing application thanks to its fast frame rates. Having it implemented on such a problem would create additional stress tests on the algorithm and may give critical feedback.

Appendix A

A.1 Integration Automation Script for CI/CD

```
1 name: Automated Review
2
3 on: [push]
4
5 jobs:
6   build:
7     runs-on: ubuntu-latest
8     strategy:
9       matrix:
10        python-version: ["3.11"]
11     steps:
12       - uses: actions/checkout@v3
13       - name: Set up Python ${ matrix.python-version }
14         uses: actions/setup-python@v3
15         with:
16           python-version: ${ matrix.python-version }
17       - name: Install dependencies
18         run: |
19           python -m pip install --upgrade pip
20           pip install pylint flake8 Flake8-pyproject pytest pytest-coverage
21           pip install numpy opencv-python scikit-image
22       - name: Checking the code using Flake8
23         run: |
24           flake8 $(git ls-files '*.py')
25       - name: Reviewing the code using Pylint
26         run: |
27           pylint $(git ls-files '*.py') --rcfile=pyproject.toml
28       - name: Running unit-tests using PyTest and PyTest-Coverage
29         run: |
30           coverage run -m pytest -v -s
```

A.2 Deployment Automation Script for CI/CD

```
1 name: Publish Python Package
2
3 on:
4   release:
5     types: [published]
6
7 permissions:
8   contents: read
9
10 jobs:
11   publish:
12     name: Publish Python Package
13     environment: release
14     runs-on: ubuntu-latest
15     permissions:
16       id-token: write
17
18     steps:
19       - uses: actions/checkout@v4
20       - name: Set up Python environment
21         uses: actions/setup-python@v3
22         with:
23           python-version: "3.10"
24       - name: Install dependencies
25         run: |
26           python -m pip install --upgrade pip
27           pip install build
28       - name: Build package
29         run: python -m build
30       - name: Publish package
31         uses: pypa/gh-action-pypi-publish@release/v1
```

A.3 The Comparison Index Algorithm in Python

```
1 import numpy
2 from skimage.metrics import structural_similarity
3
4 from core.image import Image
5 from core.utils import get_fft_of_image
6
7
8 def harmonic_radius(y_pred: Image,
9                   y_true: Image,
10                  success_thres: float = 0.95) -> float:
11     """Calculate the Harmonics Radius' index.
12     :param y_pred: The predicted image.
13     :param y_true: The ground truth image.
14     :return: The Harmonics Radius' index.
15     """
16     # Check the shapes of the parameters.
17     if y_true.get_shape() != y_pred.get_shape():
18         raise ValueError("y_true and y_pred must have the same shape.")
19
20     # Get the 2D magnitude spectrum in log scale.
21     fft_of_true: numpy.ndarray = get_fft_of_image(
22         y_true.get_image(), scale_log=True)
23     fft_of_pred: numpy.ndarray = get_fft_of_image(
24         y_pred.get_image(), scale_log=True)
25
26     # Find the center point.
27     pred_x_center = fft_of_pred.shape[0] // 2
28     pred_y_center = fft_of_pred.shape[1] // 2
29
30     # Get the smallest side.
31     smallest_side = fft_of_pred.shape[0] \
32         if fft_of_pred.shape[0] < fft_of_pred.shape[1] \
33         else fft_of_pred.shape[1]
34
35     # Assign the grid size to the smallest side.
36     grid_size = smallest_side
37     while True:
38         # Get the grid.
39         grid_pred = fft_of_pred[
40             pred_x_center - grid_size//2: pred_x_center + grid_size//2,
41             pred_y_center - grid_size//2: pred_y_center + grid_size//2,
42         ]
43         grid_true = fft_of_true[
44             pred_x_center - grid_size//2: pred_x_center + grid_size//2,
45             pred_y_center - grid_size//2: pred_y_center + grid_size//2,
46         ]
47
48         # Check the SSIM of the grid.
49         ssim_result = structural_similarity(
50             grid_true,
51             grid_pred,
52             data_range=fft_of_true.max() - fft_of_true.min(),
53             multichannel=False,
54         )
55
56         if ssim_result > success_thres:
57             # The radius is the half of the grid size.
58             found_radius: int = grid_size / 2
59             image_radius: int = smallest_side / 2
60             metric_value = (found_radius / image_radius) * 100
61             return metric_value
```

```
62
63     # Decrease the grid size by 2.
64     grid_size -= 2
65
66     # A stop condition.
67     if grid_size < 5:
68         break
69
70     # If the radius is not found, return the minimum radius.
71     return 0
```

A.4 An Example Code that Calculates Metrics with Defined API

```
1  """
2  Main application script
3  """
4
5  from core.metrics import (
6      MeanSquaredError,
7      HarmonicsRadius,
8      StructuralSimilarityIndex,
9      PeakSignalToNoiseRatio
10 )
11
12 from core.settings import SRAnalyzerSettings
13 from core.image import Image
14 from core.sr_analyzer import SRAnalyzer
15 from core.preprocessors import (
16     shrink_to,
17     linear_upscale,
18     bicubic_upscale,
19     nearest_upscale,
20 )
21
22
23 if __name__ == "__main__":
24     # Add images.
25     TRUE_IMAGE_PATH = "true_image.png"
26     MODEL_RESULT_PATH = "model_result_image.png"
27
28     high_resolution_image = Image(TRUE_IMAGE_PATH, name="high_resolution")
29     low_resolution_image = Image(TRUE_IMAGE_PATH, name="low_resolution",
30                                 preprocess=lambda img: shrink_to(img, 512, 512))
31     zero_order_image = Image(low_resolution_image, name="zero_order_upscaled",
32                              preprocess=lambda img: nearest_upscale(img, 2))
33     linear_image = Image(low_resolution_image, name="linear_upscaled",
34                          preprocess=lambda img: linear_upscale(img, 2))
35     bicubic_image = Image(low_resolution_image, name="bicubic_upscaled",
36                           preprocess=lambda img: bicubic_upscale(img, 2))
37     model_result_image = Image(MODEL_RESULT_PATH, name="super_resolution")
38
39     # Create the analyzer.
40     analyzer = SRAnalyzer(
41         SRAnalyzerSettings(name="SuperResolution Example")
42     )
43
44     # Add metrics.
45     analyzer.add_metric(HarmonicsRadius())
46     analyzer.add_metric(MeanSquaredError())
47     analyzer.add_metric(StructuralSimilarityIndex())
48     analyzer.add_metric(PeakSignalToNoiseRatio())
49
50     # Add images.
51     analyzer.add_reference_image(high_resolution_image)
52     analyzer.add_image(zero_order_image)
53     analyzer.add_image(linear_image)
54     analyzer.add_image(bicubic_image)
55     analyzer.add_image(model_result_image)
56
57     # Calculate the metrics.
58     results = analyzer.calculate()
59     for result in results:
60         print(result)
```

A.5 Training and Inferencing Algorithm for BasicSR-based Models

Figure A.1: The training workflow for BasicSR-based models.

REFERENCES

- [1] Xiangyu Chen, Xintao Wang, Jiantao Zhou, Yu Qiao, and Chao Dong. Activating more pixels in image super-resolution transformer. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, pages 22367–22377, June 2023.
- [2] Xintao Wang, Ke Yu, Shixiang Wu, Jinjin Gu, Yihao Liu, Chao Dong, Chen Change Loy, Yu Qiao, and Xiaoou Tang. ESRGAN: enhanced super-resolution generative adversarial networks. *CoRR*, abs/1809.00219, 2018.
- [3] Xiangyu Chen, Xintao Wang, Jiantao Zhou, Yu Qiao, and Chao Dong. Activating more pixels in image super-resolution transformer, 2023.
- [4] Sina Farsiu, Dirk Robinson, Michael Elad, and Peyman Milanfar. Advances and challenges in super-resolution. *International Journal of Imaging Systems and Technology*, 14(2):47–57, 2004.
- [5] Damber Thapa, Kaamran Raahemifar, William R. Bobier, and Vasudevan Lakshminarayanan. A performance comparison among different super-resolution techniques. *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, 54:313–329, 2016.
- [6] I. Begin and F.P. Ferrie. Comparison of super-resolution algorithms using image quality measures. In *The 3rd Canadian Conference on Computer and Robot Vision (CRV'06)*, pages 72–72, 2006.
- [7] Saeed Anwar, Salman Khan, and Nick Barnes. A deep journey into super-resolution: A survey, 2020.
- [8] Jari Korhonen and Junyong You. Peak signal-to-noise ratio revisited: Is simple beautiful? In *2012 Fourth International Workshop on Quality of Multimedia Experience*, pages 37–38, 2012.
- [9] Jim Nilsson and Tomas Akenine-Möller. Understanding ssim, 2020.

- [10] Manish Narwaria, Weisi Lin, Ian Vince McLoughlin, Sabu Emmanuel, and Liang-Tien Chia. Fourier transform-based scalable image quality measure. *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, 21(8):3364–3377, 2012.
- [11] Dina Yaqoob Alsaka, Çağlar Arpali, and Serap Altay Arpali. A comparison of iterative fourier transform algorithms for image quality estimation. *Optical Review*, 25(5):625–637, 2018.
- [12] I.P. Gunawan and M. Ghanbari. Image quality assessment based on harmonics gain/loss information. In *IEEE International Conference on Image Processing 2005*, volume 1, pages I–429, 2005.
- [13] Richard Zhang, Phillip Isola, Alexei A. Efros, Eli Shechtman, and Oliver Wang. The unreasonable effectiveness of deep features as a perceptual metric, 2018.
- [14] Weilong Hou, Xinbo Gao, Dacheng Tao, and Xuelong Li. Blind image quality assessment via deep learning. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, 26(6):1275–1286, 2015.
- [15] Jongyoo Kim and Sanghoon Lee. Deep learning of human visual sensitivity in image quality assessment framework. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, July 2017.
- [16] Richard H. Wiggins, H. Christian Davidson, H. Ric Harnsberger, Jason R. Lauman, and Patricia A. Goede. Image file formats: Past, present, and future. *RadioGraphics*, 21(3):789–798, 2001. PMID: 11353125.
- [17] Graham Hudson, Alain Léger, Birger Niss, István Sebestyén, and Jørgen Vaaben. JPEG-1 standard 25 years: past, present, and future reasons for a success. *Journal of Electronic Imaging*, 27(4):040901, 2018.
- [18] Greg Roelofs. Linux gazette: history of the portable network graphics (png) format. *Linux Journal*, 1997(36es):19–es, 1997.
- [19] Dietmar Wueller and Ulla Kejser. Standardization of image quality analysis – iso 19264. *Archiving Conference*, 2016:111–116, 04 2016.
- [20] Xintao Wang, Liangbin Xie, Ke Yu, Kelvin C.K. Chan, Chen Change Loy, and Chao Dong. BasicSR: Open Source Image and Video Restoration Toolbox, February 2022.

- [21] Xintao Wang, Liangbin Xie, Chao Dong, and Ying Shan. Real-esrgan: Training real-world blind super-resolution with pure synthetic data. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV) Workshops*, pages 1905–1914, October 2021.
- [22] Xintao Wang, Liangbin Xie, Chao Dong, and Ying Shan. Real-esrgan: Training real-world blind super-resolution with pure synthetic data. In *International Conference on Computer Vision Workshops (ICCVW)*, 2021.
- [23] Eirikur Agustsson and Radu Timofte. Ntire 2017 challenge on single image super-resolution: Dataset and study. In *The IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) Workshops*, July 2017.
- [24] Radu Timofte, Eirikur Agustsson, Luc Van Gool, Ming-Hsuan Yang, Lei Zhang, Bee Lim, et al. Ntire 2017 challenge on single image super-resolution: Methods and results. In *The IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) Workshops*, July 2017.
- [25] Radu Timofte, Shuhang Gu, Jiqing Wu, Luc Van Gool, Lei Zhang, Ming-Hsuan Yang, Muhammad Haris, et al. Ntire 2018 challenge on single image super-resolution: Methods and results. In *The IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) Workshops*, June 2018.
- [26] Andrey Ignatov, Radu Timofte, et al. Pirm challenge on perceptual image enhancement on smartphones: report. In *European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV) Workshops*, January 2019.
- [27] Ronald N. Bracewell. The fourier transform. *Scientific American*, 260(6):86–95, 1989.
- [28] Todd A. Ell and Stephen J. Sangwine. Hypercomplex fourier transforms of color images. *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, 16(1):22–35, Jan 2007.
- [29] Robert Fisher, Simon Perkins, Ashley Walker, and Erik Wolfard. Frequency filter.
- [30] Manuel Fritsche, Shuhang Gu, and Radu Timofte. Frequency separation for real-world super-resolution. In *2019 IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision Workshop (ICCVW)*, pages 3599–3608, 2019.

- [31] Chitwan Saharia, Jonathan Ho, William Chan, Tim Salimans, David J Fleet, and Mohammad Norouzi. Image super-resolution via iterative refinement. *arXiv:2104.07636*, 2021.